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Supplementary appendix

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Exploring environmental and distributional impacts of different transition pathways for healthier and sustainable diets – an economic modelling study

Appendix

Supplementary tables and figures 1

Model description..... 10

 MAGNET a modular CGE model..... 10

 Bio-based sectors capturing spillovers in non-food sectors 11

 EL diet affordability 11

 Context-specific diets based on global diet recommendations 12

 Demand system, income and own price elasticities 13

Validation of the calibrated income elasticities 16

Limitations of the modelling approach in this study..... 19

Region and sector detail in the MAGNET model set-up for this study 20

Scenario set-up and quantification 26

Results of sensitivity analyses..... 35

References 42

Supplementary tables and figures

Figure S- 1: Decomposing drivers of change in intake by food group and region from 2025 to 2050

Figure S- 1: Decomposing drivers of change in intake by food group and region from 2025 to 2050 (continued)

Note: Model regions grouped by World Bank income classification. All regional aggregates are population weighted averages to account for differences in country size. The Business-as-Usual (BAU) component includes the impact of changes in population which changes regional weights from 2025 to 2050. The effect of interactions between interventions is computed as the difference between the policy bundle minus the sum over the impacts of each single intervention run separately. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Table S- 1: Change in calories compared to the BAU scenario (calories/capita/day, 2050)

		HIC		UMIC		LMIC		LIC	
		EED	PB	EED	PB	EED	PB	EED	PB
Limited processing	Dairy	-163	-11	-28	1	-3	-2	-1	-3
	Fish	2	2	3	0	9	0	14	1
	Fruit & veg.	33	12	39	15	91	12	117	15
	Other crops	-29	0	-26	0	-8	-1	-9	-1
	Poultry & eggs	-69	-3	-57	-1	-3	-1	0	0
	Pulses & nuts	147	4	125	8	65	15	73	24
	Red meat	-175	-34	-160	-28	-17	-1	-31	-10
	Staples	97	-2	-215	-11	-474	-22	-285	-10
Processed food	Beverages	-1	8	-13	5	3	2	-18	2
	Other processed food	82	24	-6	12	19	11	-34	6
	Sugar	-118	0	-63	0	-51	1	-12	0
	Vegetable oils	4	-1	225	-2	401	3	351	-6
	Out-of-home consumption	72	4	75	1	37	1	34	0
Total calories		-118	3	-101	0	69	18	199	18

Note: EED = Exogenous shift to EAT-Lancet diet, PB = Policy bundle. Model regions grouped by World Bank income classification: HIC = high-income, UMIC = upper middle-income, LMIC = lower middle-income, LIC = low-income. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Table S- 2: Change in share by main channel (% change compared to BAU scenario, 2050)

		HIC		UMIC		LMIC		LIC	
		EED	PB	EED	PB	EED	PB	EED	PB
Limited processing		-10	-3	-21	-1	-27	-1	-18	0
Processed food		2	3	20	2	57	2	39	-1
Out-of-home consumption		33	1	60	1	30	0	74	-1

Note: EED = Exogenous shift to EAT-Lancet diet, PB = Policy bundle. Model regions grouped by World Bank income classification: HIC = high-income, UMIC = upper middle-income, LMIC = lower middle-income, LIC = low-income. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Table S- 3: Total and per capita GHG emissions by scenario (2050)

		HIC	UMIC	LMIC	LIC	World
Total emissions (GtCO ₂ eq)	Business-as-Usual (BAU)	17.3	33.7	17.0	3.5	71.5
	Exogenous EL diet (EED)	16.9	32.7	15.3	2.6	67.4
	Policy bundle (PB)	14.1	25.8	12.9	2.6	55.3
Population (billion)	-	1.2	2.9	4.0	1.3	9.5
Emissions per capita (tCO ₂ eq/capita)	Business-as-Usual (BAU)	13.9	11.5	4.2	2.7	7.6
	Exogenous EL diet (EED)	13.6	11.2	3.8	2.0	7.1
	Policy bundle (PB)	11.3	8.8	3.2	2.0	5.8
Percentage of per capita HIC emission rate (%)	Business-as-Usual (BAU)	100	83	31	20	54
	Exogenous EL diet (EED)	100	82	28	15	53
	Policy bundle (PB)	100	78	28	18	52

Note: Model regions grouped by World Bank income classification: HIC = high-income, UMIC = upper middle-income, LMIC = lower middle-income, LIC = low-income. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Table S- 4: GHG emissions by sector in the BAU and changes in emissions by scenario (2050)

		HIC	UMIC	LMIC	LIC
Business-as-Usual (GtCO ₂ eq)	Primary sectors	1.7	2.9	3.5	2.0
	Manufacturing & mining	8.0	21.0	7.9	0.5
	Services	4.4	6.1	3.9	0.8
	Final demand	3.1	3.6	1.8	0.2
	Total	17.3	33.7	17.0	3.5
Exogenous shift to EL diet (% change wrt BAU)	Primary sectors	-41	-37	-20	-30
	Manufacturing & mining	1	1	-6	-14
	Services	2	0	-9	-23
	Final demand	6	-1	-14	-51
	Total	-2	-3	-10	-27
Policy bundle (% change wrt BAU)	Primary sectors	-30	-29	-49	-33
	Manufacturing & mining	-21	-26	-25	-40
	Services	-4	-6	-5	-6
	Final demand	-27	-35	-17	-10
	Total	-18	-24	-24	-27

Note: Model regions grouped by World Bank income classification: HIC = high-income, UMIC = upper middle-income, LMIC = lower middle-income, LIC = low-income. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Table S-5: Import dependency household consumption (% change to the BAU, 2050)

		HIC	UMIC	LMIC	LIC	World
Exogenous EL diet (EED)	Dairy	7	17	11	10	10
	Fish	-3	38	-29	1571	19
	Fruit & vegetables	0	61	246	1747	56
	Other crops	32	24	18	32	3
	Poultry & eggs	18	13	16	14	8
	Pulses & nuts	-19	13	-3	1129	13
	Red meat	11	28	-18	22	-28
	Staples	32	-16	69	57	38
	Beverages	-6	-2	-3	-3	-3
	Other processed food	-7	-4	30	104	1
	Sugar	6	-36	38	34	14
	Vegetable oils	3	28	47	27	37
	Non-food	0	0	-3	-7	0
Policy bundle (PB)	Dairy	0	-8	-7	33	-3
	Fish	-6	12	-4	-22	4
	Fruit & vegetables	1	22	27	-6	8
	Other crops	1	0	-3	-5	0
	Poultry & eggs	9	-2	-4	3	2
	Pulses & nuts	-2	18	18	-1	9
	Red meat	-5	-20	16	493	-5
	Staples	-5	-8	-6	0	-5
	Beverages	0	-1	-3	0	0
	Other processed food	0	-2	-3	-3	-1
	Sugar	-3	2	0	-3	-1
	Vegetable oils	1	-4	2	-4	-1
	Non-food	0	0	0	8	0

Note: Model regions grouped by World Bank income classification: HIC = high-income, UMIC = upper middle-income, LMIC = lower middle-income, LIC = low-income. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Figure S- 2: Share of food groups in minimum cost of the EL diet by scenario and region (2050)

Note: BAU = Business-as-Usual, EED = Exogenous shift to EL diet, PB = policy bundle. Model regions grouped by World Bank income classification: HIC = high-income, UMIC = upper middle-income, LMIC = lower middle-income, LIC = low-income. 2025 = 2025 reference year, Source: MAGNET simulations.

Table S- 6: Change in minimal cost of the EL diet and household income by region and scenario (2050)

		HIC	UMIC	LMIC	LIC	World
Minimal cost of the EL diet (% change to the BAU)	EED	9.4	4.7	39.4	34.7	26.1
	PB	-7.6	-2.4	-2.4	-11.1	-4.4
	PB_E	0.9	0.2	3.6	3.6	2.1
	NI	0.9	0.4	3.2	1.8	1.8
	AP	-2.5	-1.7	-0.9	-0.3	-1.4
	GHG	3.8	4.2	2.7	0.2	3.6
	GHG_S	-8.1	-5.6	-11.6	-33.5	-11.9
Household income (% change to the BAU)	EED	-0.4	0.0	0.0	10.1	0.2
	PB	-0.9	-2.5	-2.7	-2.8	-2.0
	PB_E	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0
	NI	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.0
	AP	0.0	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.0
	GHG	-0.8	-2.1	-2.7	-3.2	-1.9
	GHG_S	-0.8	-2.3	-2.6	-3.4	-2.0

Note: Model regions grouped by World Bank income classification: HIC = high-income, UMIC = upper middle-income, LMIC = lower middle-income, LIC = low-income. EED = Exogenous shift to EL diet, PB = policy bundle., PB_E == exogenous shift to policy bundle diet, NI = Nudging & information, AP = Align fiscal policies by removing taxes and subsidies, GHG = GHG taxes, GHG_S = Primary sector GHG taxes subsidize encouraged food sectors. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Table S- 7: Change in cost of EL diet food groups by region and scenario (% change to the BAU, 2050)

		Staples	F&V	P&N	Fish	Poultry	Dairy	Red meat	Other	Total cost
HIC	2025	23	25	13	10	11	10	13	15	16
	EED	-2	10	82	9	-3	-4	-4	1	9
	ALL	12	-29	-30	-19	4	6	5	4	-8
	NI	0	3	4	-1	0	0	0	0	1
	AP	0	-11	-6	-14	3	4	3	1	-3
	GHG	9	3	3	4	4	4	5	1	4
	GHG_S	10	-26	-32	-20	4	4	5	2	-8
UMIC	2025	21	21	11	7	6	6	6	17	12
	EED	-8	7	87	-1	-5	-4	-6	6	5
	ALL	10	-15	-18	-7	1	3	21	5	-2
	NI	0	2	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
	AP	0	-4	-4	-6	1	1	3	0	-2
	GHG	8	2	3	1	3	6	24	3	4
	GHG_S	9	-20	-25	-19	3	6	23	4	-6
LMIC	2025	-5	-16	-9	15	2	15	-11	-2	-2
	EED	-15	102	190	1	-5	-3	-9	14	39
	ALL	11	-5	-15	-12	0	4	5	1	-2
	NI	0	10	7	0	0	0	-1	1	3
	AP	0	-2	-3	-3	0	2	1	0	-1
	GHG	9	2	2	-1	2	7	9	-1	3
	GHG_S	13	-25	-31	-32	3	5	10	0	-12
LIC	2025	3	-12	-9	-13	-2	1	0	-10	-8
	EED	-19	148	329	-21	-20	-16	-15	5	35
	ALL	10	-25	-25	-32	-3	4	45	1	-11
	NI	0	8	7	-1	-1	-1	0	0	2
	AP	0	-1	-2	-1	1	1	2	0	0
	GHG	2	-5	-5	-10	-3	7	54	-5	0
	GHG_S	13	-64	-56	-82	0	8	58	0	-33
World	2025	8	2	0	8	4	10	-1	5	4
	EED	-12	67	163	-2	-7	-5	-8	9	24
	ALL	11	-14	-19	-14	1	4	15	3	-4
	NI	0	6	5	0	0	0	0	0	2
	AP	0	-4	-4	-5	1	2	2	0	-1
	GHG	8	1	1	-1	2	6	19	0	3
	GHG_S	11	-29	-33	-33	2	5	20	2	-12

Note: Decreases in costs marked in green. F&V = fruit & vegetables, P&N = pulses & nuts. Model regions grouped by World Bank income classification: HIC = high-income, UMIC = upper middle-income, LMIC = lower middle-income, LIC = low-income. 2025 = 2025 reference year, BAU = Business-as-Usual, EED = Exogenous shift to EL diet, PB = policy bundle., NI = Nudging & information, AP = Align fiscal policies by removing taxes and subsidies, GHG = GHG taxes, GHG_S = Primary sector GHG taxes subsidize encouraged food sectors. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Table S- 8: Workers for which minimum cost of EL diet is 50% or more of daily wage, by region and scenario (2050)

		HIC	UMIC	LMIC	LIC	World
<i>Million workers</i>	BAU	0.3	30	500	389	920
	EED	0.3	30	579	438	1048
	PB	0.3	30	515	394	940
	PB_E	0.3	30	503	393	926
<i>Share of workforce (%)</i>	BAU	0.1	2.4	33.8	67.9	24.3
	EED	0.1	2.5	39.0	76.3	27.7
	PB	0.1	2.5	34.7	68.7	24.8
	PB_E	0.1	2.4	34.0	68.5	24.5

Note: Model regions grouped by World Bank income classification: HIC = high-income, UMIC = upper middle-income, LMIC = lower middle-income, LIC = low-income. BAU = Business-as-Usual, EED = Imposing the EL diet, PB = policy bundle, PB_E = exogenous shift to policy bundle diet. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Table S- 9: Workers for which minimum cost of EL diet is 50% or more of daily wage, by macro sector (2050)

		Primary production	Manufacturing & mining	Services	Manufacturing & services	All sectors
<i>Million workers</i>	BAU	564	140	215	356	920
	EED	643	152	253	405	1048
	PB	585	138	217	355	940
	PB_E	567	142	217	359	926
<i>% change to BAU</i>	EED	14.0	8.2	17.4	13.8	13.9
	PB	3.6	-1.7	0.9	-0.1	2.2
	PB_E	0.5	1.6	0.5	0.9	0.7

Note: BAU = Business-as-Usual, EED = Imposing the EL diet, PB = policy bundle, PB_E = exogenous shift to policy bundle diet. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Table S- 10: Workers for which minimum cost of EL diet is 50% or more of daily wage, by primary sector groups (2050)

		Encouraged	Discouraged	Other food	Non-food	Total primary sector
<i>Million workers</i>	BAU	127	70	304	63	564
	EED	295	43	254	51	643
	PB	164	60	302	59	585
	PB_E	146	61	298	62	567
<i>% change to BAU</i>	EED	132.3	-37.7	-16.6	-19.6	14.0
	PB	28.7	-13.3	-0.9	-6.3	3.6
	PB_E	14.8	-12.9	-2.0	-1.5	0.5

Note: BAU = Business-as-Usual, EED = Imposing the EL diet, PB = policy bundle, PB_E = exogenous shift to policy bundle diet. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Table S- 11: Total number of workers by sector and scenario (2050)

		Encouraged	Discouraged	Other food	Non-food	Total primary sector	Total manufacturing & services
<i>Million workers</i>	BAU	270	129	433	146	978	2803
	EED	486	75	366	130	1057	2725
	PB	305	115	430	141	992	2790
	PB_E	294	115	425	145	980	2802
<i>% change to BAU</i>	EED	79.7	-42.2	-15.3	-11.1	8.0	-2.8
	PB	12.9	-10.7	-0.7	-3.2	1.4	-0.5
	PB_E	8.9	-10.6	-1.7	-0.9	0.2	-0.1
<i>Change from BAU (mil.)</i>	EED	216	-54	-66	-16	79	-79
	PB	35	-14	-3	-5	13	-13
	PB_E	24	-14	-7	-1	2	-2

Note: BAU = Business-as-Usual, EED = Imposing the EL diet, PB = policy bundle, PB_E = exogenous shift to policy bundle diet. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Model description

Global computable general equilibrium (CGE) modelling allows exploration the implications of shifting diets for consumption, production, prices and income in a consistent economic framework. A global CGE covers production and consumption of all goods and services but excludes financial markets. CGE models are based on utility maximizing consumers and profit maximizing producers simultaneously interacting in markets for goods and services (commodities), and markets of endowments or production factor (land, labour, capital). Prices adjust such that supply and demand in all markets (commodities and endowments) are in equilibrium, while simultaneously satisfying the budget constraint on consumption. This household income that constrains expenditure is endogenous as it is determined by endogenous prices on endowments, which may also vary in supply depending on prices. In a global CGE model the markets include bilateral trade between regions, thus capturing changes in global supply chains. The model is solved as a nonlinear system of equations and thus does not require an explicit optimization goal - the response of producers and consumers to changing prices determines the new economic equilibrium. Feedback between changes in the food system and the rest of the economy are captured by including agricultural, manufacturing, services and factor (land, labour, capital) markets. While endogenous prices are the core driver, other mechanisms can be introduced altering or overruling the response of economic actors to changing prices, like shifting consumer preferences in line with a healthier diet.

MAGNET a modular CGE model

We use MAGNET¹, a global CGE extended to better capture details and dynamics of the bio-economy. MAGNET is built in a modular set-up around a core derived from the GTAP v7 model² and solved using the GEMPACK software³. The MAGNET database built upon version 11b database⁴ extended with module specific data where needed. A noteworthy change from the standard GTAP database covering 65 sectors and products, is the introduction of additional sectors (123 sectors in the MAGNET database) some of which produce multiple products (140 products in the MAGNET database). A key extension for bio-economy analyses is the endogenous land supply module. This module captures the dynamics between agricultural land supplied and land prices, using an asymptotic function to impose a constrained on expansion accounting for protected areas and other restrictions^{5,6}. In regions with high land pressure any additional demand results in a substantial land price increase limiting land expansion. In land abundant regions operating close to the asymptote small land price increases lead to substantial increase in agricultural land use. These different responses results in different outcomes for other factors (labour and capital) and land productivity. The land supply module is based on FAO data on agricultural land use combined with information provided by the IMAGE model⁷. Another key addition of MAGNET is segmented agricultural and non-agricultural factors markets building on the GTAP-AGR model⁸. This module is based on empirical evidence that the mobility of labour between the agricultural and non-agricultural sector is imperfect reflected by structurally lower agricultural wages^{9,10}. Three extensions of MAGNET address key aspects of moving towards an EAT-Lancet (EL) diet: bio-based sectors and environmental impacts, food affordability, and context-specific implications of global diet recommendations.

Bio-based sectors capturing spillovers in non-food sectors

Additional sector detail includes the use of biomass for fuel or as input in industries, for example to produce bioplastics. This adds more detail to feedback effects from changes in non-food biobased sectors¹¹ which may reduce environmental gains from a diet shift¹². Non-food sectors using biomass will increase demand for land if a global food demand contraction lowers agricultural prices making biomass more competitive compared to fossil-based inputs. In addition, sector-specific production functions allow substitution of land with feed or fertilizer, inducing extensification when land prices decrease. Both mechanisms may undo the contraction in agricultural land use from a diet shift. Consumption of non-food GHG intensive commodities may also increase when food expenditures decrease, partly undoing GHG reductions achieved in food production. GHG emissions include the emissions from changes in land use cover, in addition to emissions from fossil fuel use or inherent to agricultural processes like methane from rice and livestock production.

EL diet affordability

Affordability is a key concern as healthy and nutritionally adequate diets are not affordable for all^{13,14}, and for a fifth of the world population costs of the EL diet exceed income¹⁵. Changes in affordability of diets depend on changes in food prices and in income, both of which are endogenous in MAGNET. As the EL diet is defined in primary contents, we need to derive prices in terms of primary content for the different commodities through which household consume food. For this we rely on our Leontief inverse (LI) calculations which provide the quantities in primary content in each commodity, taking into account food processing and international trade in global supply chains (described below in the section on how we impose EL diet recommendations). We impute the prices of primary content by dividing the household expenditure on a commodity by the primary content contained in that commodity. We then compute the minimum cost of the EL diet by multiplying EL diet quantities by food group to the lowest cost food item mapping to each food group. In case multiple items map to a food based dietary guideline we use the lowest price to establish the minimum cost of the EL diet based on (region-specific) EL diet quantities. For example, the cereals recommendation can be met by rice, wheat or other grains. We multiply the recommended quantity of cereals with the price for each of these three cereal types and then use the one with the lowest cost as the minimum cost of meeting the EL diet recommendation for cereals.

Household food expenditures and primary content are endogenous in MAGNET and adjust in response to global changes in demand, supply and trade. The imputed price of the minimum cost of the EL diet computed from these variables is thus also endogenous and captures economywide adjustments in each scenario. MAGNET has less product detail (30 products) than in empirical assessments using household surveys or retail databases, especially for processed foods. Despite using highly aggregated food items our estimate of the minimal cost of the EL diet in 2025 (2.9 – 4.8 2017 PPP \$) lies within the range of an empirical study of costs of different diets using detailed product data¹⁶ and align with fruit and vegetables accounting for the largest cost share¹⁷.

Both the EL diet quantities (see next section) and prices are region-specific resulting in a context-specific cost of the EL diet. Affordability is then measured by expressing the cost of the EL diet relative to average household total income. Reliance on data from national accounts implies that income changes can only be modelled for one representative household by model region. To assess

changes in within-region income we also compute the diet cost as a share of daily wage. These wages vary by five types of workers and 77 sectors providing an endogenous distribution of labour income. Such a wage-based affordability measure is especially relevant for those relying on wage income alone and also food insecurity monitoring¹⁵. Wages per workers are highly heterogeneous as we have two types of segmentation: (1) limited mobility between agricultural and non-agricultural sectors maintaining persistently lower wages in agricultural sectors as empirically observed^{9,10}; (2) a post-simulation calculation of wages by sector which vary between sectors due to unobserved differences in skills of workers. The latter largely maintains the initial distribution of wages in line with empirical evidence that this distribution is stable over time¹⁸.

Wages in the MAGNET database are imputed by dividing wage payments (based on the GTAP database⁴) by the number of workers (by sector and labour type). The initial number of workers is constructed by using the total number of employed workers from ILOSTAT (<https://ilostat.ilo.org/>) and two sources of sectoral wage patterns. The first provides wage patterns by occupation and sectors observed in GTAP version 9 data from IMPACTecon (www.impactecon.com). These have limited sectoral variability being derived from highly aggregate ILOSTAT sector definitions. We therefore combine these with World Bank data providing wage differences derived from micro level databases and aggregated to 65 GTAP sectors but lacking occupational detail¹⁹. MAGNET-specific sectors are assumed to inherit the relative wage of GTAP sector from which they are split. The number of workers follows the ILO definition of employment which implies that it does not account for the hours worked. In case of part-time workers wages imputed with this employment number will underestimate wages. The total number of workers by region and occupation is projected to future periods exogenously (see the baseline scenario description below). Their allocation across sectors is determined endogenously and driven by prices in the factor markets for each occupation.

Context-specific diets based on global diet recommendations

A diet module allows steering diets in primary content measured in physical units like grams without exogenously imposing the consumption of specific food items. It relies on an endogenous variable tracing changes in the primary content of processed foods from changes in production and global trade flows, an extension of an earlier MAGNET studies^{12,20}. Defining a diet shift in terms of primary content of food items purchased by consumers allows context-specific responses, including regional variations in the consumption of unprocessed, processed and out-of-home consumption and their response to price and income changes. The definition of diets in terms of primary contents is based on tracing all direct and indirect material flows by deriving a Leontief Inverse (LI) from material balances. Material balance based on the Multi-Regional Input Output (MRIO) tables are derived from the MAGNET database tables. To assure consistent balances in physical terms we convert dollar-values in the MAGNET model database into quantities by removing all non-material components, including transport costs, import tariffs and export subsidies. In addition, we excluding intermediate use of primary commodities not contained in final household food demand, such as crops fed to animals. An extensive description of our approach can be found in an earlier study²⁰.

While we cannot compute the LI within a simulation, we treat the LI as a variable partly updated during simulations to capture changes in trade flows and primary input use in processed food sectors for more precise targeting of diet changes. We also shift primary contents of processed food & food services (out-of-home consumption) in response to changes in consumption. This avoids the collapse

of the food services sectors if primary contents would have been left fixed at reference data levels, for example forcing consumers to abandon restaurants to satisfy a reduction meat consumption. The food consumption data in physical units used in this study were provided by Dr. Marco Springmann. These data are based on FAO's Food Balance Sheet data and were corrected for food loss and waste (FLW)²¹ and thus represent food intake.

Demand system, income and own price elasticities

MAGNET uses a modified version of the standard GTAP demand system to better capture changes in food consumption patterns over time, especially key for lower income regions where incomes may rise fast in the time-horizon of the scenarios. The standard GTAP model uses a Constant-Differences-of-Elasticities (CDE) demand system to model private consumption². Income and price elasticities are derived from the IPC database using an AIDADS demand system with calibration to the GTAP data²². The advantage of a CDE demand system is that it is non-homothetic, allowing changes in household income to drive changes in commodity expenditure shares. Despite being non-homothetic income elasticities are found to remain relatively stable when income levels change substantially. Consequently, the expenditure shares remain unchanged when household income is changing²³. As a result, Engel's law (food expenditure share decreases when household income increases), does not hold when using the standard GTAP CDE demand system. Capturing Engel's law is essential in economies with strong economic growth, else food demand is overestimated and non-food demand underestimated. Apart from missing structural change in the economy towards non-food production which affects for example wages, it also is key to assess the extent to which consumption differs from the EL diet recommendations.

To capture a transition in expenditure shares in line with Engel's law we adjust the income elasticities over time with real GDP per capita corrected for purchasing power parity (PPP)¹. Income elasticities in MAGNET are calibrated on a derived relationship between income elasticities from the GTAP data and PPP corrected real GDP per capita data from the Groningen Growth and Development Center. To maintain a consistent demand system the price elasticities are also adjusted when calibrating the MAGNET demand system. Compared to the income elasticities from the GTAP database, the calibrated elasticities used in MAGNET are substantially lower for food commodities (Figure S-3). Calibrated price elasticities in MAGNET are lower for non-food commodities and other food (including food services) compared to GTAP (Figure S-4).

Figure S-3: Income elasticities used in the MAGNET model and the GTAP database by model region

Figure S-4: Price elasticities used in the MAGNET model and the GTAP database

Validation of the calibrated income elasticities

There are no global empirical databases compatible with the MAGNET database to validate the calibrated income elasticities. Income elasticities are key for lower income countries where incomes may rise fast during the time-horizon of our scenarios, like the five African regions for which we found estimates²⁴ with reasonable match to our data in terms of commodities and regions. Our calibrated income elasticities are lower, as with the comparison to the GTAP data. Apart from a very limited regional scope these estimates are not derived with a demand system including non-food commodities as required for a CGE model.

Figure S-5: Relationship between income and shares of food and non-food observed in GTAP databases and projected by the MAGNET model

Note: Colours indicate the observations by year. Warm colours in panel A for the shares observed in GTAP databases. Cool colours in panel B for the years projected by the MAGNET model. Source: author’s calculations.

Lacking data, we focused on validating the changes in expenditure shares when incomes rise, which is the main concern regarding the income elasticities in the context of this study. Combining data from various GTAP database⁴ releases we compiled data for 2004, 2007, 2011, 2014, 2017 and 2019. From this database we derived changes in income and expenditure shares on aggregated categories food and non-food commodities and for main food groups including processed-food and food services. There is a clear and non-linear relation between the log of the expenditure shares and the log of real GDP per capita in the GTAP databases (Panel A, Figure S-5). Expenditure shares of food decrease when GDP per capita increases in line with Engel's law. The food and non-food expenditure shares projected by the MAGNET model in the Business-as-usual (BAU) scenario (Panel B, Figure S-5) match the pattern observed in the GTAP databases. The expenditure pattern resulting from the calibrated demand system in the MAGNET model thus satisfies Engel's law and matches changes observed across GTAP databases.

Apart from the share of food in household expenditures the pattern across main food groups is important for our diet-focused analysis. We therefore compare the expenditure shares in the GTAP databases with MAGNET projections by main food groups. Changes in expenditure shares by food group projected by the MAGNET model (Panel B, Figure S-6) match those observed in the GTAP databases (Panel A, Figure S-6). With rising incomes only the expenditure share of food services increases. It signals that the decreasing share of income spent on food observed in Figure S-5 shifts towards out-of-home consumption. Expenditure shares of all other food groups decrease, and most strongly for cereals and the aggregated fruit and vegetables group. For cereals this is in line with Bennett's law that expenditures on staples decline with rising incomes. Expenditure shares of fruit and vegetables should, however, increase according to Bennett's law. As GTAP has less detail than the MAGNET database fruits, vegetables, pulses, nuts, and roots and tubers can only be assessed as an aggregate. A decreasing importance of the starchy root and tuber staples may dominate the pattern for this heterogeneous group.

To confirm that it is indeed the roots and tubers driving the violation of Benett's law observed in Figures S-6 we analyse the food consumption in terms of energy intake. Relying on the MAGNET model with a more detailed representation of food items than GTAP and using the LI calculations of primary content we can get a more precise assessment of how consumption patterns shift than provided by budget shares. Income growth from 2017-2050 is highest in the low-income and lower middle-income regions due to income convergence assumptions in the business-as-usual (BAU) scenario. This drives the stronger shifts in intake (Figure S-7). The share of staples (cereals, roots and tubers) in total energy intake decreases in all regions in line with Benett's law. The share of fruit & vegetables and pulses & nuts remains stable (low-income) or increases (middle-income) regions. There is a small decrease in high-income regions which start from a higher intake in 2019 and appear to shift towards more processed foods given the increase in sugar. In terms of animal sourced foods all regions are in line with Benett's law with shares rising especially fast (15%) in the low-income and lower middle-income regions. These lower income regions also seem to shift to more processed foods as sugar is the second fastest growing food group. The analysis shows that our BAU projections for 2050, which we use as the basis for our diet scenarios, reflect changes in diet patterns in line with Engel's and Benett's law.

Panel A
Expenditure shares by income compiled from GTAP (2004, 2007, 2011, 2014, 2017 and 2019)

Panel B
Expenditure shares by income projected by the MAGNET model (2019-2025)

Figure S-6: Relationship between income and expenditure shares observed in GTAP databases and projected by the MAGNET model

Note: Colours indicate the observations by year. Warm colours in panel A for the shares observed in GTAP databases. Cool colours in panel B for the years projected by the MAGNET model. Source: author's calculations.

Figure S-7: Index of the share of total energy (kcal) consumption (1 = 2017) between 2017 and 2050 by region and food group

Note: Staples = cereals and roots & tubers, FVPN = fruit & vegetables and pulses & nuts. Animal proteins = beef, lamb, pork poultry, fish and dairy. Model regions grouped by World Bank income classification. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Limitations of the modelling approach in this study

The breadth of scope of our global CGE comes at a cost of limited product, producer and household heterogeneity, and not capturing spatial differences in environmental impacts. Limited detail on processed foods prevents us from capturing shifts to cheaper but less healthy processed foods, for example in terms of salt or saturated fat. The shift from minimally processed to processed food and out-of-home consumption when shifting exogenously to the EL diet is a rough indication of such a change occurring when food prices increase. Despite using highly aggregated food items, our estimate of the minimal cost of the EL diet in 2025 (2.9 – 4.8 2017 PPP \$) lies within the range of an empirical study of costs of different diets using detailed product data¹⁶ and align with fruit and vegetables accounting for the largest cost share¹⁷.

Including only one representative household per model region our model lacks heterogeneity of within-region household income. Our 2025 affordability of the EL diet in terms of average household income falls in the middle of the range found in a detailed empirical study¹⁷ for the low-income regions (88% of daily income), in the bottom fifth percentile for lower (29%) and upper middle-income regions (12%) and below the range for high-income regions (3%). Our study thus seems to overestimate affordability in higher income regions, likely due to variability in processed foods which we are unable to capture, and skewed income distributions not being visible in average household

income. Additional within-household heterogeneity of impacts across age groups, gender, and education are also beyond the scope of our model.

Lacking within-region household heterogeneity we provide an assessment of affordability of EL diets based on daily wages. Affordability in terms of wages is also key for poor workers relying on labour for income¹⁵. We cannot account for non-labour income (which would increase available income), nor the number of dependents per worker (which decreases per capita income). Using 50% of the daily wages as a measure of affordability aligns with earlier studies^{15,25} and brings our 2025 reference year global estimates (38% of workers unable to afford the EL diet) close to a household income based assessment³ (44% of people unable to afford a healthy diet).

We measure environmental damages with GHG emissions and agricultural land use. While considered good proxies for environmental damages like biodiversity loss²⁶ these provide only a partial assessment of environmental impacts which tend to be highly spatially heterogeneous.

The CGE model has been calibrated based on empirical data which may not properly capture behavioural responses to fundamental changes in the food system. Such longer run consumer and producer responses are not included in the current analyses and warrant future research as economywide feedback will be complex, leaving the net impact undetermined. For example, nudging and information may alter preferences such that consumers become more responsive to GHG taxes consistent with these information signals. Producers may alter their production technologies in response to changing prices, for example investing in productivity increases of encouraged sectors as prices rise or in technologies to reduce reliance on fossil-based inputs in response to GHG taxes. While increased consumer responsiveness to price incentives and increased productivity of encouraged sectors could move diets closer to EL recommendations, producer investment in technologies reducing GHG emissions would reduce tax revenues and thus subsidies for encouraged sectors which would reduce the price-induced diet shift. Furthermore, the scope for changes in production technologies are highly region-specific. Lower income countries with high current yield gaps have more scope for improving yields beyond the (converging) productivity gains assumed in the BAU scenario. Any changes in relative productivity will generate global feedback effects via international trade which may alter results.

Region and sector detail in the MAGNET model set-up for this study

The 160 GTAP regions in the MAGNET database are aggregated for computational reasons into 28 model regions (Figure S-8). We started our grouping from the 13 regions used in AgMIP studies (Agricultural Model intercomparison and Improvement Project). This allows regional aggregation of our model results to a level where findings can be meaningfully compared to similar analyses using other models. We then sub-divided these regions based on a combination of (i) requirements for baseline shocks (e.g. distinguishing the EU27 to allow implementation of changes in the Common Agricultural Policy); (ii) income groups as defined by the World Bank as income per capita correlates strongly with differences in both consumption and production patterns; (iii) adherence to the EAT-Lancet diet in 2017 to assure we do not combine countries with opposing diet patterns which would lose regional variation in challenges of meeting the diet; (iv) geographical location to group regions in similar conditions in terms of production circumstances and access to global markets (e.g. landlocked

or not). While including some individual countries the final grouping aims to provide archetypes of different contexts and thus challenges faced by policymakers. Note that due to aggregate GTAP regions which comprise multiple countries with limited data some mappings may appear puzzling. For example, Greenland while being part of Denmark is combined with other regions for which no data are available in the GTAP Rest of North America (xna) region. Given the global nature of the model we need to allocate all regions. The large economic size of the United States the combination effectively means the xna region does not affect the model results. The regional aggregation of the GTAP regions¹ and correspondence to standard AgMIP reporting regions is provided in Table S-12.

For computational reasons we also aggregate the 140 commodities in the MAGNET database to 90 commodities maintaining all available detail on food products. Table S-13 describes the commodities used in the model and their connection to standard GTAP sectors as well as concordances with aggregates used in the paper.

Figure S-8: Map of the regional aggregation used in this MAGNET application

¹ For a description of the countries associated with the GTAP regions see the GTAP V11 database documentation (<https://www.gtap.agecon.purdue.edu/databases/v11/>).

Table S-12: Regional aggregation

Aggregate AGMIP	AgMIP	Model region description	Code	WB ^{a)}	GTAP region ^{b)}
North America	Canada	Canada	CAN	HIC	can
	USA	USA	USA	HIC	usa, xna
S&C America	Brazil	Brazil	BRA	UMIC	bra
	Other S&C America	Mexico	MEX	UMIC	mex
		Central America & Caribbean	CAM	UMIC	cri, gtm, hnd, nic, pan, slv, xca, dom, hti, jam, pri, tto, xcb
		Middle-income South America	SAM	UMIC	bol, col, ecu, per, ven, xsm
		Higher income South America	SAH	HIC	arg, chl, pry, ury
Former Soviet Union Europe	Former Soviet Union	Former Soviet Union (incl. Mongolia)	FSU	UMIC	mng, blr, rus, ukr, xee, kaz, kgz, tjk, uzb, xsu, arm, aze, geo
		Western EU27	EU15	HIC	aut, bel, dnk, fin, fra, deu, grc, irl, ita, lux, mlt, nld, prt, esp, swe
		Eastern EU27	EU12	HIC	bgr, hrv, cyp, cze, est, hun, lva, ltu, pol, rou, svk, svn
		High-income Europe	EURH	HIC	gbr, che, nor, xef
		Balkan	EURB	UMIC	alb, srb, xer
	Africa & Middle East	Middle East/North Afr.	Turkey	TUR	UMIC
Middle East			ME	UMIC	bhr, irn, irq, isr, jor, kwt, lbn, omn, pse, qat, sau, syr, are, xws
North Africa			NAF	LMIC	dza, egy, mar, tun, xnf
Sub-Saharan Afr.		Western Africa	WAF	LMIC	ben, cmr, civ, gha, gin, nga, sen, tgo, xwf, cog, gnq, gab, xac
		Central Africa	CAF	LIC	bfa, mli, ner, caf, ted, cod
		North-Eastern Africa	NEAF	LIC	eth, sdn, xec
		Eastern Africa	EAF	LIC	com, ken, mdg, mwi, moz, rwa, tza, uga, zmb, zwe
	Southern Africa	SAF	UMIC	mus, bwa, swz, nam, zaf, xsc	
Southern Asia	China	China	CHN	UMIC	chn, hkg
	India	India	IND	LMIC	ind
	South-East Asia	Indonesia	IDN	LMIC	xoc, idn
		Lower income South-East Asia	SEAL	LMIC	xea, khm, lao, phl, vnm, xse
		Upper middle-income South-East Asia	SEAU	UMIC	brn, mys, tha
		High- income South-East Asia	SEAH	HIC	jpn, kor, twn, sgp
Other Asia	East-Asia (excl. India)	EAS	LMIC	afg, bgd, npl, pak, lka, xsa	
Australia/New Zealand	Australia/New Zealand	Australia/New Zealand	ANZ	HIC	aus, nzl, xtw

Note: ^{a)} World Bank income groups used in the paper: HIC = high-income, UMIC = upper middle-income, LMIC = lower middle-income, LIC = low-income. ^{b)} At <https://www.gtap.agecon.purdue.edu/databases/v11/> a full listing of the GTAP regions of the Version 11 database is provided. To aid interpretation, regions consisting of single countries are coded using ISO country codes, while regions starting with an x comprise multiple countries for which incomplete data require the use of data from similar regions to derive a complete description of the world economy as required for a global CGE.

Table S-13: Commodities

Type	Code	Description	GTAP ^{a)}	Main group	Food group
<i>Primary agriculture</i>					
Staples	pdr	Paddy and processed rice	pdr	Staples	Cereals
	wht	Wheat	wht	Staples	Cereals
	grain	Cereal grains nec	gro	Staples	Cereals
	roots	Roots and tubers	v_f	Staples	Roots & tuber
Fruit, & veg	veg	Vegetables	v_f	Fruit & vegetables	Vegetables
	fruit	Fruit	v_f	Fruit & vegetables	Fruits
	nuts	Nuts	v_f	Fruit & vegetables	Nuts & seeds
	pulses	Pulses	v_f	Fruit & vegetables	Pulses
Other food crops	oils	Oil seeds	osd	Other crops	Oil seeds
	sug	Sugar cane, sugar beet	c_b	Other crops	Sugar
	crops	Crops nec	ocr	Other crops	Other
Non-food crops	oagr	Other agriculture	pfb	Other crops	NonFood
Livestock	othctl	Sheep, goats, horses	ctl	Livestock	Beef & lamb
	cattle	Cattle	ctl	Livestock	Beef & lamb
	pigpls	Pig and other animal products	oap	Livestock	Pork
	pltry	Poultry	oap	Livestock	Poultry
	milk	Raw milk	rmk	Livestock	Dairy
Non-food livestock	wol	Wool, silk-worm cocoons	wol	Livestock	NonFood
Fish	wfish	Wild fish	fsh	Fish	Fish
	aqcltr	Aquaculture	fsh	Fish	Fish
	Swd	Seaweed	fsh	Fish	Fish

Table S-13: Commodities, continued

Type	Code	Description	GTAP ^{a)}	Main group	Food group
Forestry	frs	Forestry	frs	forestry	NonFood
	plan	Plantation	frs	forestry	NonFood
Crop residues	r_pdr	Residue pdr	pdr	Residues	NonFood
	r_gro	Residue gro	gro	Residues	NonFood
	r_osd	Residue osd	osd	Residues	NonFood
	r_frs	Residue frs	frs	Residues	NonFood
Manure	mnctl	Manure cattle	ctl	Manure	NonFood
	mnbctl	Manure beef cattle	ctl	Manure	NonFood
	mnoap	Manure other animals	oap	Manure	NonFood
	mnrnk	Manure milk cattle	rnk	Manure	NonFood
	mnptry	Manure poultry	oap	Manure	NonFood
<i>Processed food</i>					
Based on crops	pcr	Processed rice	pcr	Staples	Cereals
	sugar	Sugar	sgr, ofd	Other crops	Sugar
	vol	Vegetable oils and fats	vol	Other crops	Oil seeds
	cvol	Crude vegetable oil	vol	Intermediates	NonFood
Based on livestock	othcmt	Meat: other cattle, sheep, goats, horse	cmt	Livestock	Beef & lamb
	bfmt	Beef meat	cmt	Livestock	Beef & lamb
	othmt	Other meat product nec	omt	Livestock	Pork
	pulmt	Poultry meat	omt	Livestock	Poultry
	dairy	Dairy products	mil	Livestock	Dairy
Based on fish	fishp	Fish processing	ofd	Fish	Fish
Composite foods	ofd	Processed food	ofd	Composite	Other
	b_t	Beverages and tobacco products	b_t	Composite	Other
<i>Animal feed</i>					
By-products	oilcake	Oil cake	vol	By-products used as feed	NonFood
	mola	Molasse	sgr	By-products used as feed	NonFood
	fishm	Fish meal	ofd	By-products used as feed	NonFood
	ddgs	Biogasoline byproduct	p_c	By-products used as feed	NonFood
Composite feed	fdctl	Feed cattle	ofd	Feed	NonFood
	fdpig	Feed pigs	ofd	Feed	NonFood
	fdplt	Feed poultry	ofd	Feed	NonFood
	fdfsh	Feed fish	ofd	Feed	NonFood
<i>Mining</i>					
Fossil fuels	coa	Coal	coa	Fossils	NonFood
	oil	Crude oil	oil	Fossils	NonFood
	gas	Gas	gas	Fossils	NonFood
	gas_dist	Gas manufacture, distribution	gdt	Energy	NonFood
Other minerals	oxt	Minerals nec	oxt	Other minerals	NonFood

Table S-13: Commodities, continued

Type	Code	Description	GTAP ^{a)}	Main group	Food group
<i>Bio-based</i>					
Energy	biog	Biogasoline	p_c	Fuel	NonFood
	biod	Biodiesel	p_c	Fuel	NonFood
	bf2nd	2nd gen biofuel	p_c	Fuel	NonFood
	respel	Residue and pellets	p_c, lum	Agri-based	NonFood
Chemicals	bioch	Bio chemicals	chm	Chemicals	NonFood
	bioph	Bio pharmaceuticals	bph	Chemicals	NonFood
	biopl	Bio plastics	sgr, chm, rpp	Chemicals	NonFood
Other use	texplus	Textile, leather & apparel	tex, wap, lea	Agri-based	NonFood
	wood	Wood products	lum	Agri-based	NonFood
	ppp	Paper products, publishing	ppp	Agri-based	NonFood
<i>Fossil-based</i>					
Energy	p_c	Petroleum, coal products	p_c	Fuel	NonFood
Chemicals	chm	Chemical products	chm	Chemicals	NonFood
	bph	Basic pharmaceuticals	bph	Chemicals	NonFood
	rpp	Rubber and plastic	rpp	Chemicals	NonFood
Fertilizers	fert_n	Fertilizer nutrient n	chm	Agriculture inputs	NonFood
	fert_p	Fertilizer nutrient p	chm	Agriculture inputs	NonFood
	fert_k	Fertilizer nutrient k	chm	Agriculture inputs	NonFood
Electricity	ely	Electricity	ely	Electricity	NonFood
	ely_c	Electricity from coal	ely	Electricity	NonFood
Fossil-based	ely_g	Electricity from gas	ely	Electricity	NonFood
	ely_n	Electricity from nuclear	ely	Electricity	NonFood
Renewable	ely_h	Electricity from hydropower	ely	Electricity	NonFood
	ely_w	Electricity from wind & solar	ely	Electricity	NonFood
	bioe	Bioelectricity 2nd gen	ely	Electricity	NonFood
	heat	Heat	ely	Heat	NonFood
	bioh	Bioheat	ely	Heat	NonFood
<i>Other manufacturing sectors</i>					
Other manufacturing sectors	manu	Manufacturing	i_s, nfm, fmp, ele, eeq, ome, mvh, otn, cns	Other	NonFood
	mmm	Mineral products nec	mmm	Extraction	NonFood
	omf	Other Manufacturing	omf	Other	NonFood
<i>Services</i>					
Food services	foodserv	Food services	afs, ros, osg, hht	Food services	Other
Other services	ser	Services	wtr, trd, whs, cmn, ofi, ins, rsa, obs, dwe	Other	NonFood
	edu	Education	edu	Other	NonFood
	trans	Transport sector	otp, wtp, atp	Energy	NonFood

Note: ^{a)} Codes of GTAP sector to which model sectors are linked. A detailed description of sectors in the GTAP version 11 database, including concordances to ISIC and CPC classifications, is available at <https://www.gtap.agecon.purdue.edu/databases/v11/>.

Scenario set-up and quantification

All diet scenarios are evaluated against anticipated changes in the global economy in the absence of new policies or interventions from 2017 (the reference year of our database) up to 2050. The macro drivers (population and GDP) are the most recent values of the “middle-of-the-road” Shared Socioeconomic Pathway 2 (SSP2) values²⁷ with a higher climate impact reflected by RCP 7.0. The occupation projections are derived by combining projected changes in population and income with historical data on changes in workforce composition. Shocks on land and agricultural productivity matching the most recent SSP2 data are provided by the IMAGE model²⁸. Additional productivity shocks reflecting higher climate impacts (RCP 7.0) than accounted for in SSP2 are imposed on crops using data provided by the IMAGE model and taken from literature for livestock²⁹ and labour³⁰. The BAU scenario projects strong income growth in the lower income regions between 2025 and 2050, but the global income distribution remains highly unequal. Changes in population and workforce diverge due to differences in age-structure, with aging populations in higher income regions (Figure S-9).

Figure S-9: BAU population and GDP per capita (2025-2050)

Note: Model regions grouped by World Bank income classification: HIC = high-income, UMIC = upper middle-income, LMIC = lower middle-income, LIC = low-income. Source: MAGNET simulations.

The diet scenarios add additional interventions on top of the BAU scenario shocks and are described in Table S-14. For the exogenous shift to the EL diet (EED) scenario, we impose that in 2050 the EL diet recommendations will be achieved in all regions through a shift in consumer preferences. Per food group, EAT-Lancet (EL) diet recommends minimum and/or maximum consumption level³¹. Following these recommendations, we define for each region an EL diet based taking the consumption pattern in the BAU scenario in 2050 into account making the EL implementation regio-specific. For example, in cases where BAU red meat consumption in 2050 is below EL recommendations the 2050 BAU levels are set as the target to avoid imposing an increase in a discouraged food group. For non-staples, the food groups exceeding the EL diet were scaled down to the recommended intakes, while encouraged

food groups with consumption levels below EL diets were set to the minimum EL intake. These consumption levels were then converted from grams into kcal. Recommended consumption levels of the staples (cereals and roots & tubers) were computed to meet the recommended daily energy target in kcal. Data on daily energy requirements are region specific²¹ with the detailed estimates needed for quantification of our scenarios provided by Dr. Marco Springmann. The resulting changes in consumption in gram/capita/day are provided Table S-15 in the EED column, alongside changes in intake in the BAU and other counterfactual scenarios. As the EL diet is imposed at food group (e.g. red meat) and not at food commodity level (beef & lamb, pork) the EED diet by region is a combination of the food group restrictions, consumer prices and preferences.

The policy bundle (PB scenario) consists of a combination of shifting consumption and adjusting taxes and subsidies. In the NI scenario we shift consumption demand using a preference shift parameter based on estimates from a systematic review³². All studies in this review were conducted in the USA, Canada and Europe. Most researched interventions were education (information) or a combination of education, training and persuasion. Examples of interventions categorized under education included students attending a course on the impact of food consumption and participants receiving SMS messages about the positive environmental and health impacts of eating less red meat. Given the short duration of the interventions and targeted groups (e.g. students) not being representative of the general population, we used the lowest reported effects of nudging and information on red meat and fruit and vegetable consumption. All estimates are based on studies in high-income countries. To obtain estimates for the other regions in our model we compute the percentage change in 2050 BAU consumption levels from the nudging and information in high income regions and apply this percentage to 2050 consumption levels in the other regions. This yields the same proportional shift across regions while taking into account regional differences in consumption. These shifts are reported in the NI (nudging & information) column in Table S-15. By fixing consumption levels in the NI scenario we can quantify a preference shifter needed to reach this change in consumption. This preference shifter is then used as an exogenous shock when combining the NI scenario with other interventions, allowing us to capture the impact of the nudging while allowing consumption levels to adjust to other interventions.

The remaining components of the policy bundle are changes in existing taxes and subsidies to align fiscal policies with EL diets (VT, RTX, RM, RSUB), introduction of GHG taxes (GHG), and redistributing primary sector GHG taxes as subsidies on sectors producing foods to be consumed more (GHG_S). These scenarios are described in Table S-14. Quantification of the alignment of fiscal policies is based on removing taxes and subsidies in the MAGNET database. While subsidies for animal feed were removed, subsidies on agricultural commodities which may also be used for food, bioplastics or fuel were kept. Given a recent estimate that 44% of the EU's agricultural subsidies goes to production of feed³³ large indirect subsidies on animal production may have remained reducing the impact of the fiscal alignment in our study. The GHG scenario imposes a GHG tax of 100 \$/ton CO₂ equivalent, based on a previous climate-focussed study using an ensemble of global economic models, including MAGNET³⁴. The changes in taxes are summarized in Table S-16 to Table S-23.

Additional sensitivity analyses on price elasticities and GHG taxation schemes are described alongside their results in a dedicated section below (p 35).

Table S-14: Description of counterfactual scenarios

Code	Description	Implementation
Imposed diet shifts		
EED	Imposing consumption of cereals, roots & tubers, fruit, vegetables, pulses, nuts, oil seeds, sugar, red meat, poultry, dairy and fish	Exogenous shock on consumption using a preference shift parameter. The EL diet was gradually introduced between 2025-2050 for each 5-year time step with a homogenous percentage change shock.
PB_E	Imposing consumption of cereals, roots & tubers, fruit, vegetables, pulses, nuts, oil seeds, sugar, red meat, poultry, dairy and fish equal to the consumption levels reached with the policy bundle (PB)	Exogenous shock on consumption using a preference shift parameter. For each 5-year time step the consumption quantities are equal to the food consumption outcomes in the policy bundle (PB).
Nudging		
NI	Imposing consumption of shifts through nudging and information at food group level to increase FVPN (fruits, vegetable, pulses, nuts) and reduce red meat consumption in 2050.	Exogenous shock on consumption to quantify a preference shifts which can be combined with other interventions. Shifts are gradually introduced between 2025-2050 for each 5-year time step with a homogenous percentage change shock.
Reducing prices		
RTXS	Removing taxes on producers and consumers related to fruit, vegetables, pulses, nuts and fish production and consumption: output taxes (TO), taxes on primary factors (TFE), subsidies on firm's (domestic and import) purchases (TFD and TFM) and private (domestic and import) consumption taxes (TPD and TPM).	The removal of taxes is implemented in all regions. All taxes related to fish feed production and consumption are also removed. In the first time step (2025-2030) the taxes were fully removed.
GHG_SUB	Subsidies on fruit, vegetables, pulses, nuts and fish production from revenues from primary sector GHG taxes through output subsidies (TO).	Revenues of primary sector GHG taxes are redistributed as subsidies within each region based on the shares in total value of production of the subsidized sectors. The subsidies are imposed in all regions. The revenues of the GHG taxes gradually increase over time in line with the introduced GHG emission tax.

Table S-14: Description of counterfactual scenarios (continued)

Code	Description	Implementation
Increasing prices		
RSUB	Removing subsidies on producers and consumers related to red meat, poultry, dairy, and sugar: output subsidies (TO), subsidies on primary factors (TFE), subsidies on firm's (domestic and import) purchases (TFD and TFM) and private (domestic and import) consumption subsidies (TPD and TPM).	<p>The removal of the subsidies on red meat, dairy and sugar consumption and production is implemented in all regions. All subsidies related to livestock and poultry feed production and consumption are also removed. In the first time step (2025-2030) the subsidies were fully removed.</p> <p>Given the substantial lower environmental and health impact of poultry consumption compared to red meat and dairy consumption, we kept the subsidies in regions with below EL recommended poultry consumption. We thus excluded regions where poultry consumption is under the EL diet recommendation in the BAU scenario in 2050 when removing poultry subsidies. The excluded regions are NAF, WAF, CAF, NEAF, EAF, IND, SEAL and EAS (see Table S-12 for region codes)</p>
Increasing prices		
GHG_A	GHG emission tax of 100 \$/ton CO2 equivalent on all primary sectors (agriculture and fishery), through an output tax (TO) based on GHG emissions (CO2, N2O, CH4, F-gases) associated with production.	The GHG tax affects primary sectors in all regions. The GHG emission tax was gradually introduced between 2025 and 2045, with for each 5-year time step a quarter of the total carbon price (25\$/ton CO2eq per time step). Between 2045 and 2050 the carbon price remained unchanged with a carbon price of \$100/ton CO2eq.
GHG	Economywide GHG emission tax of 100 \$/ton CO2 equivalent on all sectors through output tax (TO) and tax on firm's domestic and import purchases (TFD and TFM) based on GHG emissions (CO2, N2O, CH4, F-gases) associated with production and inputs.	The GHG tax affects all sectors in all regions. The GHG emission tax was gradually introduced between 2025 and 2045, with for each 5-year time step a quarter of the total carbon price (25\$/ton CO2eq per time step). Between 2045 and 2050 the carbon price remained unchanged with a carbon price of \$100/ton CO2eq.

Note: # The description of scenarios aligning fiscal policies refers to tax definitions used in the standard GTAP v7 model² at the core of the MAGNET model. These are added to support the replication of our scenarios by other CGE modelers using the GTAP database.

Table S-15: Change in per capita food intake 2025-2050 (gram/capita/day)

		<i>Change wrt 2025 (g/cap/day)</i>				<i>Change by intervention (g/cap/day)</i>						
		BAU	PB	PB E	EED	PB	NI	AP	GHG A	GHG N	GHG S	
Beef & lamb	HIC	3.9	-4.6	-3.9	-11.6	-8.4	-4.4	-1.1	-6.9	0.4	0.0	
	LIC	4.1	-1.5	-1.6	-8.6	-5.6	-2.5	-0.1	-4.5	-0.1	-0.1	
	LMIC	1.9	-0.6	-0.4	-7.0	-2.6	-1.0	-0.1	-1.8	0.0	0.0	
	UMIC	3.1	-2.7	-1.5	-9.6	-5.8	-2.6	-0.2	-4.9	0.3	0.0	
Cereals	HIC	2.4	9.8	7.0	3.1	7.4	2.4	0.3	-2.4	5.6	1.2	
	LIC	15.4	11.8	13.0	3.6	-3.7	-1.6	-0.2	-0.2	-0.5	-4.8	
	LMIC	-5.5	-11.1	-14.3	-2.6	-5.6	-1.9	0.0	-5.6	2.7	-2.8	
	UMIC	-1.7	-2.9	-2.6	-0.7	-1.2	1.0	0.2	-4.2	1.8	0.1	
Dairy	HIC	31.8	15.4	15.9	3.7	-16.4	-0.3	-14.6	-13.6	3.1	1.0	
	LIC	11.0	5.7	6.0	7.5	-5.3	-0.7	-0.1	-6.3	0.0	-0.1	
	LMIC	3.7	1.4	1.9	1.2	-2.3	-0.9	-1.3	-3.1	1.0	0.3	
	UMIC	16.3	15.6	16.9	8.9	-0.7	-0.9	-0.9	-6.2	3.2	0.0	
Fish	HIC	0.3	5.1	4.9	16.2	4.8	-0.3	2.9	-0.6	0.6	5.8	
	LIC	0.5	1.6	1.5	22.6	1.0	-0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	1.8	
	LMIC	0.6	1.8	1.8	6.4	1.2	-0.4	0.2	0.0	0.3	2.1	
	UMIC	-0.7	0.2	0.1	0.4	0.9	-0.3	0.5	-0.2	0.3	2.6	
Fruits	HIC	9.3	38.0	30.6	22.4	28.7	19.0	-0.7	-0.1	2.4	7.9	
	LIC	14.5	36.1	35.6	38.4	21.5	11.7	0.2	0.8	-0.1	19.0	
	LMIC	3.8	19.5	18.8	18.3	15.7	11.7	0.3	-0.1	0.4	5.7	
	UMIC	7.6	27.4	25.8	17.0	19.8	13.8	0.4	-0.3	0.6	6.0	
Nuts & seeds	HIC	-0.5	0.9	0.5	6.0	1.4	1.0	-0.5	-0.2	0.3	0.5	
	LIC	0.0	0.4	0.4	17.2	0.4	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	
	LMIC	-0.9	0.7	0.4	6.0	1.6	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.3	
	UMIC	0.3	1.8	1.2	19.6	1.5	0.7	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.7	
Oil seeds	HIC	2.7	4.5	3.6	6.3	1.8	0.5	0.2	-0.9	1.8	0.1	
	LIC	3.2	2.7	3.3	8.3	-0.5	-0.3	-0.1	0.8	-0.4	-1.0	
	LMIC	1.4	2.5	1.4	7.2	1.0	0.0	-0.1	0.6	0.5	-0.2	
	UMIC	2.0	2.1	2.0	4.6	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1	
Other crops	HIC	1.5	2.3	1.7	16.7	0.9	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.8	0.1	
	LIC	0.4	0.5	0.4	10.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	-0.1	
	LMIC	-0.3	-0.2	-0.3	-3.2	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
	UMIC	0.5	0.7	0.7	10.6	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	
Pork	HIC	3.8	-4.2	-4.7	-7.7	-8.0	-6.8	-1.4	-2.2	0.6	0.1	
	LIC	1.4	0.5	0.3	10.0	-0.9	-0.8	0.0	-0.2	0.0	-0.1	
	LMIC	1.1	0.3	0.2	4.9	-0.8	-0.6	0.0	-0.3	0.0	0.0	
	UMIC	0.3	-5.9	-6.1	-12.8	-6.2	-6.2	-0.3	-0.7	0.4	0.1	
Poultry	HIC	8.6	5.1	4.7	5.9	-3.5	-0.9	-2.5	-2.9	1.1	0.0	
	LIC	1.5	1.3	1.2	22.9	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	
	LMIC	4.6	4.0	4.0	19.3	-0.7	-0.2	0.0	-0.8	0.1	0.0	
	UMIC	7.3	6.7	6.7	8.8	-0.7	-0.5	-0.4	-1.3	0.7	0.1	

Table S-15: Change in per capita food intake 2025-2050 (gram/capita/day), continued

		Change wrt 2025 (g/cap/day)				Change by intervention (g/cap/day)						
		BAU	PB	PB_E	EED	PB	NI	AP	GHG_A	GHG	GHG_S	
Pulses	HIC	0.2	1.2	1.1	15.3	1.0	0.8	0.0	-0.1	0.2	0.2	
	LIC	0.4	8.0	8.1	19.9	7.5	4.5	0.1	0.6	0.1	6.8	
	LMIC	-0.6	4.3	3.7	16.4	5.0	3.0	0.2	0.1	0.3	2.1	
	UMIC	1.1	3.3	2.8	28.4	2.1	1.2	0.0	-0.1	0.2	1.2	
Roots & tuber	HIC	1.9	3.1	2.7	2.9	1.2	-0.1	0.0	-0.6	1.8	0.3	
	LIC	24.7	30.2	29.4	10.0	5.5	-2.8	0.0	7.6	1.1	-4.1	
	LMIC	17.7	17.8	17.5	15.2	0.1	-1.1	0.1	0.2	0.6	0.0	
	UMIC	1.3	1.9	2.1	1.7	0.7	0.1	0.0	-0.4	1.0	0.2	
Sugar	HIC	7.2	7.4	8.2	10.1	0.2	0.6	-0.5	-0.5	1.0	-0.4	
	LIC	2.4	2.5	2.4	7.0	0.2	0.1	0.0	1.2	-0.8	-0.3	
	LMIC	0.0	0.3	0.4	0.6	0.3	0.3	-0.1	0.8	0.0	-0.6	
	UMIC	6.0	6.7	6.5	12.6	0.7	0.2	0.1	0.9	0.3	-0.4	
Vegetables	HIC	0.5	23.7	25.1	11.8	23.2	22.1	-0.6	-0.1	2.7	3.1	
	LIC	0.4	13.0	13.1	21.0	12.6	7.0	0.2	1.0	0.1	9.7	
	LMIC	-3.4	15.5	15.1	11.6	18.9	14.2	0.4	0.0	0.8	5.0	
	UMIC	-13.1	19.3	18.5	4.8	32.5	25.5	0.6	-1.1	1.5	8.7	

Note: Model regions grouped by World Bank income classification: HIC = high-income, LIC = low-income, LMIC = lower middle-income, UMIC = upper middle-income. Scenario codes refer to business-as-usual (BAU), a policy bundle of nudging, information and price incentives with repurposing of primary sector GHG taxes as subsidies on foods to consume more (PB), exogenous shift to policy bundle diet (PB_E), exogenous shift to the EL diet (EED). Decomposition of the impact of the policy bundle as difference to the BAU: total impact (PB), nudging and information (NI), aligning fiscal policies by removing taxes and subsidies (AP), primary sector GHG taxes (GHG_A), GHG taxes on the whole economy (GHG), GHG taxes on the whole economy with repurposing of primary GHG taxes as subsidies on foods to consume more (GHG_S). Source: MAGNET simulations.

Table S-16: Change in output tax between 2025 and 2050 (% points)

Food group	Region			
	High	Upper middle	Lower middle	Low
Beef & lamb	0.21	0.01		0.52
Pork	1.21	0.02		0.24
Poultry	0.9	0.02		
Dairy	0.32	0.09		0.75
Sugar	0.15	0.1	0.01	0.98
Vegetables	-0.63	-0.1	-0.09	-0.04
Pulses	-0.43	-0.3	-0.5	-0.02
Nuts & seeds		-0.18	-0.05	-0.03
Fish	-2.61	-0.2	-0.31	-0.09

Note: See description of the scenarios (Table S-14) for more details and link to scenarios.

Table S-17: Change in tax on firm's purchases of intermediate inputs between 2025 and 2050 (% points)

Food group	Region			
	High	Upper middle	Lower middle	Low
Beef & lamb	0.67	0.36	0.06	
Pork	0.19	0.96	0.05	
Poultry	0.23	0.86		
Dairy	0.02	0.61	1.07	
Sugar	0.1	0.67	0.5	
Vegetables	-1.64	-0.01	-0.13	-0.97
Pulses	-0.12	-0.05	-6.85	-0.29
Nuts & seeds	-0.16	-0.06	-0.38	-1.04
Fish	-0.45	-0.47	-0.39	-3.95

Note: See description of the scenarios (Table S-14) for more details and link to scenarios.

Table S-18: Change in tax shock on firm's purchases of primary factors between 2025 and 2050 (% points)

Endowment	Food group	Region			
		High	Upper middle	Lower middle	Low
Capital	Beef & lamb	5.65	1.84	0.05	
	Pork	3.15	2.84	0.09	
	Poultry	1.41	2.12	0.07	
	Dairy	3.47	1.3	0.27	
	Sugar	0.23	1.13	0.13	
	Vegetables	-0.23	-0.06	-0.13	-0.24
	Pulses	-0.95	-0.2	-0.12	-0.18
	Nuts & seeds	-0.69	-0.21	-0.66	-0.32
	Fish	-3.16	-1.52	-0.11	-0.12
Labour	Beef & lamb	0.04	0.46		
	Pork	0.01	1.02		
	Poultry	0.03	0.63		
	Dairy	0.04	0.06		
	Sugar	0.01	0.26		
	Vegetables	-30.44	-2.74	-0.83	-1.21
	Pulses	-12.93	-12.73	-0.94	-1.16
	Nuts & seeds	-18.93	-14.45	-2.36	-0.89
	Fish	-28.19	-2.82	-1.07	-1.19
Land	Beef & lamb	17.21	3.89	26.46	
	Dairy	37.19	1.93	2.07	
	Sugar	37.74	0.56	0.03	
	Vegetables	-0.07	-0.2	-0.06	-0.23
	Pulses	-0.71	-0.47	-0.04	-0.17
	Nuts & seeds	-0.1	-0.23	-0.33	-0.32
	Fish				

Note: See description of the scenarios (Table S-14) for more details and link to scenarios.

Table S-19: Change in tax on private household purchases between 2025 and 2050 (% points)

Food group	Region			
	High	Upper middle	Lower middle	Low
Beef & lamb	0.25			
Pork	0.23			
Poultry	0.02			
Dairy	0.13			
Sugar	0.02			
Vegetables	-2.23	-0.18	-0.07	-0.09
Pulses	-4.84	-1.15	-0.18	-0.22
Nuts & seeds	-5.48	-0.47	-0.26	-0.23
Fish	-2.63	-0.41	-0.06	-0.18

Note: See description of the scenarios (Table S-14) for more details and link to scenarios.

Table S-20: Impact of economywide GHG tax shock on output tax between 2025 and 2050 (% points)

Food group	Region			
	High	Upper middle	Lower middle	Low
Beef & lamb	9.6	14.89	17.26	57.93
Pork	2.44	3	9.49	18.25
Poultry	1.64	2.73	7.81	6.95
Dairy	1.62	2.69	5.83	24.83
Sugar	0.05	0.13	0.1	0.09
Vegetables	0.75	0.28	0.33	0.82
Fruits	0.4	0.1	0.11	0.13
Pulses	1.33	1.01	0.06	0.15
Nuts & seeds	0.36	0.18	0.22	0.15
Fish				
Cereals	2.73	3.38	3.02	3.83
Roots & tuber	0.84	0.55	0.14	0.18
Oil seeds	1.29	1.08	0.48	0.2
Other			0.01	0.02
NonFood	0.2	0.8	1.38	3.23

Note: See description of the scenarios (Table S-14) for more details and link to scenarios.

Table S-21: Impact of primary sector GHG tax shock on output tax between 2025 and 2050 (% points)

Food group	Region			
	High	Upper middle	Lower middle	Low
Beef & lamb	9.63	14.8	17.16	57.28
Pork	2.43	2.95	9.35	17.91
Poultry	1.64	2.71	7.7	6.76
Dairy	1.62	2.66	5.87	24.27
Sugar	0.05	0.12	0.09	0.08
Vegetables	0.75	0.29	0.34	0.81
Fruits	0.41	0.1	0.11	0.13
Pulses	1.34	1.02	0.06	0.15
Nuts & seeds	0.36	0.18	0.22	0.15
Fish				
Cereals	2.75	3.37	3.05	3.79
Roots & tuber	0.84	0.55	0.14	0.18
Oil seeds	1.29	1.08	0.48	0.19
Other			0.01	0.01
NonFood				

Note: See description of the scenarios (Tabel S-14) for more details and link to scenarios.

Table S-22: Impact of redistributing primary sector GHG taxes as subsidies on output tax between 2025 and 2050 (% points)

Food group	Region			
	High	Upper middle	Lower middle	Low
Vegetables	-24.11	-16.84	-28.78	-76.67
Fruits	-28.56	-25.57	-30.33	-76.73
Pulses	-38.54	-42.07	-31.52	-76.64
Nuts & seeds	-35.05	-22.09	-29.69	-66.42
Fish	-25.97	-20.88	-32.98	-77.73

Note: See description of the scenarios (Tabel S-14) for more details and link to scenarios.

Table S-23: Impact of economywide GHG tax shock on firm's purchases tax between 2025 and 2050 (% points)

Food group	Region			
	High	Upper middle	Lower middle	Low
Non-food	0.18	0.35	0.5	0.59

Note: See description of the scenarios (Tabel S-14) for more details and link to scenarios.

Results of sensitivity analyses

Price changes and the household response to these are key for our model results. To explore the robustness of our findings we conduct two sets of sensitivity analyses. The first is on the price elasticities in our demand system, which govern the extent to which household consumption responds to price changes. Apart from the two scenarios where a diet change is set exogenous irrespective of its costs (EED, PB_E), all counterfactual scenarios use taxes and subsidies which alter consumer prices directly or indirectly. The magnitude of the price elasticities thus determines the effectiveness of the majority of policies explored in this study. We defined three sensitivity scenarios where we increased the price elasticity with 0.05 of (1) animal products (beef & lamb, pork, poultry and dairy); (2) fruit & vegetable and pulses & nuts; and on (3) both animal products and fruit & vegetable and pulses & nuts combined. The absolute increase in the price elasticities makes increases in price elasticities differ by region and commodity. We only explored an increase in price elasticities which increases the impact of the taxes and subsidies of our policy bundle. Not only leaves the policy bundle a substantial gap with the EL diet recommendations which could be reduced by increasing elasticities altering our conclusions. The combination with nudging and information and signals on environmental damage from the GHG taxes may also make consumers more responsive to the price signals in line with our sensitivity analysis of the price elasticities.

The second set of sensitivity analyses focuses on the GHG tax as the magnitude of the GHG tax might lead to different feedback or spillover effects in the global economy. For this sensitivity analysis we compared the policy bundle with a carbon price of 100 US\$/ton CO₂eq with a carbon price of 20 US\$/ton CO₂eq and a carbon price of 190 US\$/ton CO₂eq. These values are based on the range used in a model comparison study³⁴ which included the MAGNET model. In addition, we conducted a scenario whereby the carbon price was distributed across the regions based on GDP per capita whereby the weighted mean of the carbon price globally was 100 US\$/ton CO₂eq. This keeps the global average CO₂ price the same as in the policy bundle, but alters the distribution over regions. The resulting carbon price ranges from 5.28 US\$/ton CO₂eq for the region Central Africa (CAF) to 275.76 US\$/ton CO₂eq for the USA. This may be seen as more just than a uniform distribution of the carbon price as high-income countries contributed substantially more to total historical GHG emitted, their per capita emissions are still higher, and it makes the level of the tax (and thus the “pain” induced) more proportional to differences in income.

Increasing price elasticities has a limited effect on food consumption. Compared to the policy bundle the increase in price elasticities for animal products leads to a smaller decrease in beef and lamb consumption (-1.4%), while other animal products increase by a maximum of 0.7% for poultry (Table S-24). The impact of the higher price elasticities is highest in low-income and lower middle-income regions. The increase in the price elasticities of fruit & vegetable and pulses & nuts leads to a moderated increase of 1.1% for both fruit & vegetables and pulses & nuts. The differences in response between animal products, and fruit & vegetable and pulses & nuts consumption is the result of differences in relatively changes in price elasticities. There are no substantial interaction effects when comparing results of increasing price elasticities of animal products, and fruit & vegetable and pulses & nuts separately, to the results of a simultaneous increase in price elasticities.

Compared to a carbon price of 100 US\$/ton CO₂eq in the policy bundle, a lower carbon price (20 US\$/ton CO₂eq) leads to 10% less reduction in beef and lamb consumption, while a higher carbon price (190 US\$/ton CO₂eq) to 6.1% more reduction (Table S-24). Differences are strongest in low-income and lower middle-income regions. This is in line with the main results that GHG taxes have the strongest impact in lower income regions with more emission-intensive production systems. With less (more) GHG tax revenues fruit & vegetable and pulses & nuts consumption were lower (higher) with a carbon price of 20 US\$/ton CO₂eq (190 US\$/ton CO₂eq). As expected GHG emissions are highest (66.0 GTonCO₂eq) with a carbon price of 20 US\$ US\$/ton CO₂eq and lowest (49.4 GTonCO₂eq) with a carbon price of 190 US\$/ton CO₂eq (Table S-25). In addition, a higher carbon price leads to higher inequality in GHG emissions. With a carbon price of 20 US\$/ton CO₂eq per capita GHG emissions in low-income regions were 54% of those in high-income regions dropping to 50% with a carbon price of 190 US\$ (Table S-25).

Total global GHG emissions of a distributed carbon price of 100 US\$/ton CO₂eq based on GDP per capita is only slightly higher (56.6 GTonCO₂eq) than with a uniform carbon price of 100 US\$/ton CO₂eq as used in the policy bundle (55.3 GTonCO₂eq). High-income regions contribute more to GHG emission reductions, while the other regions reduce their emissions less as GHG taxes are lower when distributed based on income (Table S-25). This leads to a convergence of per capita emissions which range from 78 to 52% of high-income emissions with a uniform GHG tax as used in the policy bundle to 92-62% with a distributed GHG tax (Table S-25). Compared to the policy bundle with the uniform GHG tax, beef and lamb consumption reduces more in high-income regions (-2.6%) but less in the other regions (6.4-17.2%). As only a small share of people live in high-income regions, average global beef and lamb consumption is higher with distributed GHG taxes (6.0%). Fruit & vegetable and pulses & nuts consumption is lower in all regions with the distributed GHG tax.

As in the main results GHG taxes lead to an extensification of crop production and increase land for non-food use. A higher GHG price leads to a further expansion of agricultural land compared to the BAU, 52 mil ha with 190 US\$/ton CO₂eq (Figure S-10). Distributing the GHG taxes based on income reduces pressure on emission-intensive agriculture in lower income regions and reduces the agricultural land expansion from 25 mil. ha with a uniform tax as used in the policy bundle to 3 mil. ha. Lowering the GHG price to 20 US\$/ton CO₂eq leads to a net contraction of agriculture land use (-7 mil. ha) as the contraction in pastureland is no longer exceeded by an expansion in crop area.

Table S-24: Difference in daily per capita consumption (%) between the policy bundle and the sensitivity analysis scenarios in 2050

		Increased price elasticity of 0.05			Carbon price per ton CO ₂ eq		
		Animal products	Fruit & vegetable and pulses & nuts	Animal products + Fruit & vegetable and pulses & nuts	20 US\$	190 US\$	100 US\$ distributed
World	Beef & lamb	-1.4	-0.1	-1.4	10.0	-6.1	6.0
	Pork	0.4	-0.1	0.3	-0.1	0.1	0.2
	Sugar	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.3	0.4	-0.7
	Poultry	0.7	-0.1	0.6	0.2	-0.6	0.1
	Dairy	0.4	-0.1	0.3	0.2	-0.5	0.0
	Fruit & veg.	0.0	1.1	1.1	-2.0	1.7	-1.5
	Pulses & nuts	0.0	1.1	1.1	-4.3	4.7	-4.8
	Fish	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-3.0	3.1	-1.5
HIC	Beef & lamb	-0.3	-0.1	-0.4	6.8	-5.6	-2.6
	Pork	0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.1
	Sugar	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.2	0.1	0.7
	Poultry	0.2	-0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.3	-0.5
	Dairy	0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.3	-0.4	-0.3
	Fruit & veg.	0.0	2.1	2.1	-2.2	1.4	-2.1
	Pulses & nuts	-0.1	1.9	1.9	-2.6	0.5	-13.2
	Fish	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-4.4	4.5	1.2
UMIC	Beef & lamb	-0.6	0.0	-0.7	9.7	-6.1	6.4
	Pork	0.6	-0.1	0.5	-0.5	0.0	-0.2
	Sugar	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.7	0.4	-1.1
	Poultry	0.6	-0.1	0.5	-0.3	-0.3	-0.1
	Dairy	0.5	-0.1	0.4	-0.4	-0.7	-0.6
	Fruit & veg.	0.0	1.6	1.5	-1.4	1.0	-0.5
	Pulses & nuts	-0.1	2.4	2.3	-4.9	3.7	-2.9
	Fish	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-1.3	1.2	-0.2
LMIC	Beef & lamb	-2.8	0.0	-2.9	11.4	-4.0	9.5
	Pork	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	2.1	-1.7	2.1
	Sugar	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.6	-1.0
	Poultry	1.3	0.0	1.2	1.5	-1.5	1.2
	Dairy	0.7	0.0	0.7	0.1	0.3	-0.1
	Fruit & veg.	0.0	-0.3	-0.3	-2.1	2.6	-1.6
	Pulses & nuts	-0.1	0.4	0.4	-4.3	6.2	-3.4
	Fish	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-3.4	3.8	-2.9
LIC	Beef & lamb	-4.1	-0.2	-4.2	15.8	-10.5	17.2
	Pork	-0.3	-0.2	-0.5	0.2	7.9	1.2
	Pulses & nuts	0.2	1.1	1.3	-4.3	3.9	-6.4
	Poultry	0.7	-0.1	0.6	0.3	0.7	0.4
	Dairy	-0.7	-0.1	-0.8	4.0	-3.6	4.5
	Fruit & veg.	0.2	1.0	1.2	-5.2	4.2	-6.3
	Pulses & nuts	0.2	1.1	1.3	-4.3	3.9	-6.4
	Fish	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	-9.2	8.6	-11.2

Note: Model regions grouped by World Bank income classification: HIC = high-income, UMIC = upper middle-income, LMIC = lower middle-income, LIC = low-income. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Table S-25: Total and per capita GHG emissions by scenario (2050)

		HIC	UMIC	LMIC	LIC	World
Total emissions (GtCO ₂ eq)	Uniform 20 US\$/ton CO ₂ eq	16.2	31.1	15.5	3.1	66.0
	Uniform 100 US\$/ton CO ₂ eq	14.1	25.8	12.9	2.6	55.3
	Uniform 190 US\$/ton CO ₂ eq	13.0	22.7	11.5	2.3	49.4
	Distrib. 100 US\$/ton CO ₂ eq	12.3	26.6	14.6	3.2	56.6
Population (billion)	-	1.2	2.9	4.0	1.3	9.5
Emissions per capita (tCO ₂ eq/capita)	Uniform 20 US\$/ton CO ₂ eq	13.0	10.6	3.9	2.5	7.0
	Uniform 100 US\$/ton CO ₂ eq.	11.3	8.8	3.2	2.0	5.8
	Uniform 190 US\$/ton CO ₂ eq	10.4	7.8	2.9	1.8	5.2
	Distrib. 100 US\$/ton CO ₂ eq	9.9	9.1	3.6	2.5	6.0
Percentage of per capita HIC emission rate (%)	Uniform 20 US\$/ton CO ₂ eq	100	82	30	19	54
	Uniform 100 US\$/ton CO ₂ eq	100	78	28	18	52
	Uniform 190 US\$/ton CO ₂ eq	100	74	27	17	50
	Distrib. 100 US\$/ton CO ₂ eq	100	92	37	25	61

Note: Model regions grouped by World Bank income classification: HIC = high-income, UMIC = upper middle-income, LMIC = lower middle-income, LIC = low-income. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Total (mil. ha):	-7	25	52	3
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Figure S-10: Global change in agricultural land area compared to Business-as-Usual (2050, mil. ha)

Note: Land use by activities is assigned to categories of use based on the material flow balances tracing the use of the produced output. For example, land use for crops is assigned to feed based on the share of livestock sectors in total demand for crops. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Figure S-11: Average household expenditure on food and non-food and minimum cost of the EL diet by price elasticity sensitivity scenario and region (2017 PPP \$/capita/day, 2050)

Note: NF = average household expenditure on non-food; FE = household food expenditure minus cost of the EL diet; EL = minimum cost of the EL diet. P = Policy bundle, P_m = Policy bundle with 0.05 increase in the price elasticities of beef & lamb, poultry and dairy; P_v = Policy bundle with 0.05 increase in the price elasticities of fruit & vegetable and pulses & nuts; P_mv = Policy bundle with 0.05 increase in the price elasticities of beef & lamb, poultry, dairy, of fruits, vegetables, pulses and nuts. Sum of the columns is the expenditure-based average household income. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Figure S-12: Average household expenditure on food and non-food and minimum cost of the EL diet by GHG tax sensitivity scenario and region (2017 PPP \$/capita/day, 2050)

Note: NF = average household expenditure on non-food; FE = household food expenditure minus cost of the EL diet; EL = minimum cost of the EL diet. Unif. \$20 = Policy bundle with uniform carbon price of 20 US\$/ton CO₂eq; Unif. \$100 = Policy bundle with uniform carbon price of 100 US\$/ton CO₂eq; Unif. \$190 = Policy bundle with uniform carbon price of 190 US\$/ton CO₂eq; Dist. \$100 = Policy bundle with distributed carbon price of 100 US\$/ton CO₂eq based on per capita GDP. The policy bundle with uniform carbon price of 100 US\$/ton CO₂eq corresponds to the policy bundle in the main analysis. Sum of the columns is the expenditure-based average household income. A negative value for FE indicates that the minimum cost of the EL diet exceeds the household food expenditures. Source: MAGNET simulations.

The increase in price elasticities has a marginal impact on affordability of the EL diet for households (Figure S-11). The largest impact is 0.4 2017 PPP \$ decrease in the costs of the EL diet in upper middle-income regions. Changes in food and non-food expenditures nor household income is altered when increasing price elasticities. The impact of the different carbon prices on EL diet affordability for household is also small (Figure S-12). Increasing GHG taxes leads to small reductions in household income. Largest impacts are in the low-income region where the EL diet costs are below the food expenditures with the policy bundle (uniform GHG tax) but exceed food expenditures in case of a distributed GHG tax. While the household income increases when GHG taxes are reduced this is not enough to compensate less tax revenues to subsidise encouraged foods.

Increasing elasticities does not affect the affordability assessment for workers compared to the policy bundle in the main text. Impacts of different GHG tax regimes varies across regions in both size and direction (Table S-26). Lowering GHG taxes to a uniform 20 US\$/ton CO₂eq reduces the number of workers unable to afford the diet with strongest effects compared to the policy bundle in the main text in high-income regions (-5.8%). The smallest effect is in low-income regions (-1.1%) where it is most of a concern as 68.7% of the workforce cannot afford the EL diet with the policy bundle (Table S-8). A uniform 190 US\$/ton CO₂eq GHG tax increases the number of workers unable to afford the EL diet in all but the high-income regions, again with the smallest effect in low-income regions (0.8%). The higher GHG tax reduces unaffordability for workers in high-income regions (-15.6%) which benefit from more efficient technologies. With a distributed GHG tax affordability of the EL diet reduces in all but the upper middle-income regions (8.7%) with smallest impact in the low-income regions (-0.7%). The level and variation in GHG taxes thus affects affordability of EL diets for workers but impacts in the lower income regions where it is most of concern are limited (1.1.% difference at most, Table S-26). Impacts of different GHG tax regimes are concentrated in the primary sectors where wages are lowest (Table S-27). The exception is a decrease in the number of workers unable to afford the EL diet in manufacturing & services sectors (-2.2%) with a uniform 190 US\$/ton CO₂eq tax. It indicates a shift to more labour-intensive production methods raising wages more than the cost of the EL diet. Reductions in unaffordability for workers in the primary sectors are again concentrated in encouraged sectors (Table S-28).

Table S- 26: Workers for which minimum cost of EL diet is 50% or more of daily wage, by region and sensitivity scenario (% difference from policy bundle scenario in main text, 2050)

	HIC	UMIC	LMIC	LIC	World
Unif. \$20	-5.8	-2.2	-2.8	-1.1	-2.1
Unif. \$190	-15.6	12.3	1.4	0.8	1.5
Dist. \$100	-5.9	8.7	-2.4	-0.7	-1.3

Note: Model regions grouped by World Bank income classification: HIC = high-income, UMIC = upper middle-income, LMIC = lower middle-income, LIC = low-income. Unif. \$20 = Policy bundle with uniform carbon price of 20 US\$/ton CO₂eq, Unif. \$190 = Policy bundle with uniform carbon price of 190 US\$/ton CO₂eq; Dist. \$100 = Policy bundle with distributed carbon price of 100 US\$/ton CO₂eq based on per capita GDP. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Table S- 27: Workers for which minimum cost of EL diet is 50% or more of daily wage, by macro sector and sensitivity scenario (% difference from policy bundle scenario in main text, 2050)

	Primary production	Manufacturing & mining	Services	Total
P_m	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0
P_v	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
P_mv	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0
Unif. \$20	-3.5	1.0	-0.2	-2.1
Unif. \$190	2.9	-2.2	-0.2	1.5
Dist. \$100	-2.3	1.7	-0.7	-1.3

Note: P_m = Policy bundle with 0.05 increase in the price elasticities of beef & lamb, poultry and dairy; P_v = Policy bundle with 0.05 increase in the price elasticities of fruit & vegetable and pulses & nuts; P_mv = Policy bundle with 0.05 increase in the price elasticities of beef & lamb, poultry, dairy, of fruits, vegetables, pulses and nuts, Unif. \$20 = Policy bundle with uniform carbon price of 20 US\$/ton CO₂eq, Unif. \$190 = Policy bundle with uniform carbon price of 190 US\$/ton CO₂eq; Dist. \$100 = Policy bundle with distributed carbon price of 100 US\$/ton CO₂eq based on per capita GDP. Source: MAGNET simulations.

Table S-28: Workers for which minimum cost of EL diet is 50% or more of daily wage, by primary sector groups and sensitivity scenario (% difference from policy bundle scenario in main text, 2050)

	Encouraged	Discouraged	Other food	Non-food	Total primary sector
P_m	0	-1	0	0	0
P_v	0	0	0	0	0
P_mv	0	-1	0	0	0
Unif. \$20	-14	5	-1	3	-3
Unif. \$190	9	-1	2	-4	3
Dist. \$100	-16	8	1	5	-2

Note: P_m = Policy bundle with 0.05 increase in the price elasticities of beef & lamb, poultry and dairy; P_v = Policy bundle with 0.05 increase in the price elasticities of fruit & vegetable and pulses & nuts; P_mv = Policy bundle with 0.05 increase in the price elasticities of beef & lamb, poultry, dairy, of fruits, vegetables, pulses and nuts, Unif. \$20 = Policy bundle with uniform carbon price of 20 US\$/ton CO₂eq, Unif. \$190 = Policy bundle with uniform carbon price of 190 US\$/ton CO₂eq; Dist. \$100 = Policy bundle with distributed carbon price of 100 US\$/ton CO₂eq based on per capita GDP. Source: MAGNET simulations.

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